

THERMOELASTIC ANALYSIS OF FOAM-CORED SANDWICH CONSTRUCTION TEE-JOINTS

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SUMMARY: The nature of load transfer through the thickness of a foam-cored sandwich construction tee-joint is analysed using the thermoelastic technique. A method for thermoelastic calibration of the quasi-isotropic foam-cored material is described. The thermoelastic results are compared to those obtained from a finite element model of the tee-joint; the differences in the results are discussed in detail.

KEYWORDS: thermoelastic stress analysis, SPATE, foam-cored sandwich structures, tee-joints, finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

The thermoelastic stress analysis technique is a now well established experimental method and has been used in a wide range of engineering applications. The technique is based on the measurement of the small temperature change induced in a material subjected to elastic cyclic stresses. In a linear elastic, isotropic, homogeneous material the temperature change is directly proportional to the sum of the principal stresses in the material [1]. The small temperature change is measured by the use of highly sensitive infra-red detectors.

The current industry standard equipment for thermoelastic stress analysis is the SPATE (Stress Pattern Analysis by Thermal Emissions) system [2]. The equipment incorporates a single cell cadmium-mercury-telluride infra-red detector. The detector unit houses two mirror drive systems which allow the detector to operate in a point-to-point scanning mode over a predefined area of a test specimen or component. Over a period of around 1 hour a full-field representation of the stresses is developed on a computer monitor. The test specimen requires only minimal surface preparation, in that a thin coating of matt black paint is applied to the surface which provides a constant emissivity and as a bonus enhances the thermoelastic response of the material.

The design and analysis of composite tee-joints is currently an area of major importance and is of particular relevance in the ship building industry. The thrust of the work has concentrated on single skin constructions [3], the interest being in the failure mode of the joint and the load transfer mechanism from the joint web to the flange. Detailed static and fatigue loading test programmes have been carried out (e.g. [4,5]). These provided the magnitude and position of the failure in joint; the data obtained from the work has been used as a basis for characterising the structures. Recently [6] a thermoelastic analysis of a single-skin tee-joint has demonstrated the potential of the technique for evaluating such structures. The work focused on the load transfer from the web to flange through the thickness of the material. The SPATE results provided

detailed full-field stress information and highlighted variations in the tee-joint structure caused by the manufacturing process.

The present paper deals with the analysis of foam-cored sandwich construction tee-joints. Thermoelastic stress analysis is particularly attractive in the analysis of foam-cored structures as the technique is non-contact and requires no supplementary attachments, such as a strain gauge, which could locally reinforce the material. SPATE scans are taken from the end of a tee-joint, subjected to combined bending and tension loading, so that the through-thickness stresses can be analysed. The results of the thermoelastic analysis are calibrated so that they can be compared with data derived from a finite element analysis of such structures. The potential of the technique in the analysis of foam-cored structures is clearly demonstrated.

TEE-JOINT CONSTRUCTION

A diagram of the tee-joint used in the thermoelastic work is shown in Fig. 1. The joint is 100 mm in width and consists of a 100 mm thick flange and a 50 mm thick web. The flange and web are 800 mm and 280 mm respectively in length. Different foam materials are used for the flange and the web; Divinycell H130 for the flange and Divinycell H80 for the web. Both the flange and the web are bounded by a 6 mm thick 1200 gm^{-2} quadriaxial (i.e. $0, 90^\circ, \pm 45^\circ$) woven roving E-glass/epoxy skin. The flange and the web are joined directly using an epoxy adhesive. A 7 mm fillet is formed at the junction of the flange and the web using colloidal silica filled epoxy. A 6 mm thick boundary angle skin consisting of 900 gm^{-2} glass/epoxy $\pm 45^\circ$ woven rovings is bonded around the fillet. A summary of the relevant material properties of the tee-joint constituents is provided in Table 1 [7].

Table 1: Properties of the tee-joint constituents

Constituent	Tensile Modulus (MPa)	Compressive Modulus (MPa)	Shear Modulus (MPa)	Compressive Strength (MPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)
Web Core	80	85	31	1.2	2.2
Flange Core	140	175	52	2.5	4.2
Laminate	17000	-	5000	240	360
Fillet Resin	3300	-	3500	-	85

THERMOELASTIC THEORY

For a linear elastic, isotropic, homogeneous material it is readily shown [1] that the small temperature change, ΔT , induced in a material under elastic cyclic loading conditions is related to the stresses in the material as follows:

$$\Delta T = K T (s_1 + s_2) \quad (1)$$

where K is the thermoelastic constant (i.e. $\alpha/\rho C$, where α is the coefficient of linear thermal expansion, ρ is the density and C is the specific heat of the material), T is the absolute

temperature of the material and $(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)$ are the changes in the principal stresses. When an infra-red detector is used the output from the detector, i.e. the thermoelastic signal, S , is related to the stresses by the following:

$$s_1 + s_2 = AS \quad (2)$$

where A is a calibration constant that is a combination of K , the detector properties and the surface emissivity of the material. In equation (2) $(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)$ are the principal stress changes on the surface of a material or test specimen. The assumption is made that the temperature change occurs adiabatically. This is ensured by cyclically loading the specimen at such a rate that no conduction can take place. Equations (1) and (2) imply that the mean stress in the specimen is of no consequence so that the temperature change is only dependent on the range of the stress. It has been shown [8] that the mean stress is important if the elastic constants of the are highly temperature dependent. For most materials, at room temperature, the temperature dependence of Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio is small and these have a negligible effect on the thermoelastic signal.

For orthotropic materials equation (2) must be modified to incorporate the different coefficients of expansion of the material [6] i.e.

$$s_p + \alpha s_t = A'S \quad (3)$$

where α is the ratio α_t/α_p , A' is a further calibration constant and the subscripts p and t denote values in the principal material directions.

In the case of the single-skin tee-joints the orthotropic boundary angle material has been analysed [6] and equation (3) must be used. Methods for determining the calibration constant A' and α are described in detail in ref. [6]. In the design of foam-cored sandwich structures it is expected that only a shear load will be carried by the core. However, initial static tests on the tee-joint [7] have shown that for certain loading cases the joints fail in compression. This is seen as an important consideration as the compressive strength of the foam is around 50% of that tensile strength (see Table 1). Therefore any significant compressive stresses developed in the core could result in early fatigue failure of the joint. Shear stresses are detected as zero stress by the SPATE system because of the nature of equation (2). Any deviations from the shear loading design condition will therefore appear prominently in the SPATE data from the foam core. In this paper only the foam core is dealt with (a full analysis of the tee-joint will be presented elsewhere); as the material is quasi-isotropic equation (2) is used as the basis for the thermoelastic work described in the following sections.

Thermoelastic Calibration Of Foam-Core Material

It is possible to derive A (see equation (2)) using material property values from the literature and the characteristics of the detector. This approach produces unreliable results mainly due to variations in the material. An experimental approach is far more reliable and also takes account of any variations in paint emissivity and detector output. A description and a critical appraisal of thermoelastic calibration techniques is given in ref. [9]. A possible approach would be to bond strain gauges to the foam material and measure the strain at that point and compare this to the thermoelastic signal. However this is impractical as the gauges will cause local reinforcement. A better approach is to devise a means of direct calibration (i.e. where the material is loaded in

such a way that the stress distribution is known). To facilitate this a block of material, 180 mm in length and of 26.5 mm x 11.5 mm cross section was machined from the flange and a block 130 mm in length and 28 x 11.5 mm cross section was machined from the web of a tee-joint. (As the flange and web incorporate different foams, a separate calibration constant is required for both.) The most straightforward means of direct calibration is to load the material in tension. In this case there is only one principal stress in the specimen (i.e. the applied stress, σ_{app}) which can be calculated by simply dividing the applied load, P, by the cross sectional area of the specimen. This value can be substituted into equation (1) so that the calibration constant, A, can be determined from the thermoelastic signal from the specimen i.e.

$$A = \frac{S_{app}}{S} \quad (4)$$

A diagram of the flange test specimen and the loading jig used in the calibration studies is shown in Fig. 2. As the foam is very weak, 1 mm thick aluminium alloy stiffeners were bonded to each end of the specimens. The load is transferred from the end grips to the foam test specimen via the two pins. These were used to ensure an even loading across the specimen and to reduce any stress concentration effects. (The web calibration specimen was identical except the length between the pins was 116 mm instead of 168 mm.) Anti-bending shackles were attached to each end of the specimens prior to the assembly being mounted in an Instron 8501 servo-hydraulic test machine. Because of the flexible nature of the specimens the load control mode of the test machine could not be used. It was therefore necessary to apply a constant longitudinal strain to the specimens of ranges 2.38×10^{-3} for the flange and 3.44×10^{-3} for the web. These were multiplied by the tensile modulus values given in Table 1 to give stress ranges of 0.45 MPa for the flange material and 0.28 MPa for the web material. Throughout the tests the straining frequency was maintained at 8 Hz.

The foam test specimens were coated with 2 passes of R.S. matt black paint before conducting the thermoelastic work. The SPATE detector was set at a working distance of 600 mm giving a scanning spot size of 0.8 mm. (This is larger than the deflection range of the specimens which was 0.4 mm and therefore negates the requirement for any motion compensation.) The average thermoelastic signal recorded for the specimens was 633 U (Uncalibrated signal unit) for the flange material and 958 U for the web material. During both tests the variations in the signal were large giving standard deviations of around $\pm 15\%$. There is a high level of "noise" in the data which can be attributed to the cellular nature of the material. Substituting the σ_{app} values and the signal values into equation (4) provides A values of 7.07×10^{-4} MPa U⁻¹ for the flange material and 2.89×10^{-4} MPa U⁻¹ for the web material. Using the detector properties and material property values from the literature A was derived as 6.12×10^{-4} MPa U⁻¹ and 3.77×10^{-4} MPa U⁻¹ the flange and web respectively. This shows a very encouraging agreement considering the variability in the material and the other error sources [9] associated with calculating A in this manner.

Fig. 1 Tee-joint configuration and dimensions of SPATE scan area

Fig. 2 Flange material calibration specimen and loading jig

Thermoelastic Analysis Of Tee-Joint

Consideration of the in-service loads experienced by the tee-joints suggested that combined bending and tension loading would most adequately model the in-service conditions. To this end a test set-up was configured in a specially designed test-rig known as FORTReSS [10] which is located at the University of Southampton. A steel beam was fixed at an angle of 45° in the FORTReSS structure. The flanges of the tee-joint were clamped symmetrically about the centre of the joint; the spacing of the clamps being 240 mm centre to centre. A hydraulic ram was positioned horizontally on the FORTReSS structure and connected to the upper end of the web. This configuration produces a combination of tensile and bending loading, i.e. a 45° pull-off load. The tee-joint was subjected to a load cycle of 0.7 ± 0.405 kN at a frequency of 8 Hz and coated with 2 passes of R.S. matt black paint prior to testing. The SPATE detector was set at a working distance of 350 mm which gave a scanning spot size of 0.6 mm. SPATE area scans were taken from both sides of the specimen, the dimensions of the scan area are shown in Fig. 1; the scans took approximately 2.5 hours to complete.

Four line plots were taken through both sets of data. The approximate positions of these are indicated in Fig. 1. Two plots (lines 1 and 2) were taken across the web; one away from the fillet the other through the root of the fillet radius. One plot (line 3) was taken along the skin on the flange. Another plot (line 4) was taken along the flange core material. Lines 1 and 2 were calibrated using the A value of 2.89×10^{-4} MPa U^{-1} and line 4 was calibrated using the A value of 7.07×10^{-4} MPa U^{-1} . The line plots from both the front and the back of the tee-joint specimen are shown in Figs. 3 and 4 respectively. (The a, b and d figures show calibrated data. The c figures are uncalibrated data for the skin material and are shown for completeness.) Fig. 3a, b and Fig. 4a, b are plots from the flange and in all cases $\sigma_1 + \sigma_2$ never exceeds 0.2 MPa; the departures at the edges are readings from the skin. This indicates, as predicted, that virtually all of the load is carried in shear. The plots through the flange skin (Figs. 3c and 4c) show positive and negative peaks at the junction with the web. The two spikes in Fig. 3c are accounted for by voids in the material at the fillet. Most interesting are the plots along the flange core shown in Figs. 3d and 4d. Here much larger stresses of the order of 0.5 MPa in compression and 1 MPa in tension are developed in positions in line with the junction of the flange and the web (i.e. 20 mm and 80 mm into the plot respectively). The plots cross zero at around 50 mm close to the centre of the joint.

Finite Element Analysis Of Tee-Joint

The finite element analysis (FEA) package used in the current work was ANSYS 5.1. The tee-joint was modelled as a two dimensional slice in plane strain with non-linear geometric properties (i.e. large deflection analysis). The element type used throughout the model was Plane82; a 2-D solid element with orthotropic material properties capability. The model was constructed of one element through the thickness of the web and flange skins, one element through the thickness of the web core and four elements through the flange core. The boundary angles consisted of one element per overlaminated layer producing four elements through the thickness at the root of the joint radius. The model was restrained to represent the clamping arrangement used during experimentation and a force vector was applied near to the top of the web to simulate the 45° pull-off. The material properties used for the foam-core and the laminated skin are given in Table 1.

To produce comparable data to that of the SPATE scan line plots shown in Figs. 3 and 4, stress results of the FEA were extracted along two lines cut through the model at the same positions as SPATE lines 2 and 4 (see Fig. 1 for line positions). Principal stress values σ_1 and σ_2 were

calculated along each line from the nodal results and then added together to produce the data required. Fig. 5 shows the FEA results for the sum of the principal stresses along lines 2 and 4. Fig. 5a shows that the stress sum through the entire core is zero indicating that the load is carried in shear. Fig. 5b shows a negative peak of -0.29 MPa 30 mm into the plot and a positive peak of 0.38 MPa 80 mm into the plot. The plot crosses zero at around 50 mm close to at the centre of the tee-joint.

DISCUSSION

The SPATE plots through the web core shown in Figs. 3a, b and 4a, b show that $(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)$ is close to zero confirming the shear carrying capability of the core and that only a small amount of bending is being carried by the core. The signal from the skin shown in Figs. 3a, b and 4a, b is high, especially in the side of the joint loaded in tension, indicating, as expected, that the skin is carrying the bending stresses. However, it should be noted that in all the SPATE line plots only the core has been calibrated and that the values shown for the skins can only be seen as a qualitative indication of the stress levels in the skin. (A further more detailed analysis of the joint is planned which will cover both the skin and the core.) Figs. 3d and 4d show that in the flange core there are significant bending stresses and these should be taken into account in any failure analysis of the entire joint. The maximum value shown in compression is around 1 MPa which is 40% of the failure load of the material and may have detrimental effects on the fatigue life of such joints. A further factor is that the load range used in the SPATE tests of 0.81 kN is low; it is expected that the joints will experience higher in-service loads which in the case of the flange core could initiate damage.

A quantitative comparison of the SPATE data from the front and rear sides of the joint shows that there is some difference in the plots, most noticeably in the line 4 (Figs. 3d and 4d). This could be attributed to some out-of-plane loading and slight alignment errors in the SPATE equipment. A more likely cause relates to the variations in the core material and other defects occurring in the manufacturing process. Fig. 3c shows a plot along the skin material and through the fillets. At the fillets (30 mm and 85 mm) there are large spikes in the data. These were caused by the absence of filler material between the boundary angle and the skin. The voids could prevent adequate load transfer into the boundary angle and result in the flange core carrying more of the load and would account for the higher stress values in Fig.4a. Further confirmation of this is the virtually identical plots obtained from both the front and back of the web which would not be affected by the voids.

There is a very good qualitative agreement between the FEA results and the SPATE data. Only the data from the core can be quantitatively compared as the FEA from the skins is just $\sigma_1 + \sigma_2$ and the SPATE data is proportional to $\sigma_p + \alpha\sigma_t$ (see equation 3). The FEA shows that in the web core there is virtually no bending. However, the SPATE data (lines 1 and 2) show that there is a slight bending load carried by the core. Comparing the data for line 4 shows a difference between the FEA and SPATE results. The FEA gives values of around 60% less than those from the SPATE. Apart from the manufacturing defects which are not modelled by FEA other factors may be contributing to this difference. Firstly, the applied load range of 1.4 kN is very low and within the noise limits of FORTReSS. This means that the actual applied load may be in error of the order of 10% to 15% and would result in differences between the experimental and predicted results. Furthermore, initial load-deflection tests [10] have shown that the FEA model under-predicts deflections (i.e. that the joints are more flexible) resulting in smaller stress values. This needs to be confirmed and further work is underway to calibrate the causes of the difference. The important feature however is that the trends predicted by the FEA are very similar to the SPATE results.

CLOSURE

The work described in the present paper to the authors' knowledge is the first thermoelastic work on foam-cored sandwich structures. The results are very encouraging and provide a full field representation of the stresses, which highlights any manufacturing defects. The work has clearly demonstrated the potential of thermoelastic analysis in the experimental evaluation of such structures. Of particular importance is the fact that the flange core material is experiencing significant bending stresses which could result in premature failure. Further work is underway to model the full range of behaviour under a variety of loading and bending conditions.

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Fig. 3 Line scans on front side of tee-joint

Fig. 4 Line scans on rear side of tee-joint

Fig. 5 Line plots derived from FEA results